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INTRODUCTION

To evaluate the proportion of people with dopaminergic deficit and positive alpha-synuclein seed amplification assay (aSynSAA) among a remotely identified group of hyposmic individuals.

BACKGROUND

Identifying people in the earliest stages of synucleinopathy may be essential for studies testing therapeutics to slow progression. Remote screening of participants may allow for efficient recruitment of large cohorts.

METHODS

People 60 and older without a diagnosis of PD were asked to complete the University of Pennsylvania Smell Identification Test (UPSIT) remotely. Eligible participants had (a) hyposmia (UPSIT < 15th %ile initially; then the threshold was reduced to 10th %ile) and (b) at least mildly abnormal DAT-SPECT (lowest putamen specific binding ratio < 100% expected for age and sex). Biological assessments included cerebrospinal fluid aSynSAA testing through Amprion.

RESULTS

As of 29-Jan-2024, 49,843 participants were provided an UPSIT remotely and 31,293 (63%) completed them. Of those, 4,639 (15%) had an UPSIT < 10th %ile and 1,546 completed DAT-SPECT. Self-reported features obtained on a screening questionnaire were independently associated with an UPSIT < 10th %ile, such as a diagnosis of REM sleep behavior disorder (RBD) or dream enactment behavior (DEB) (aOR: 1.9, 95% CI 1.7 – 2.1) and problems with smell (aOR: 15.0, 95% CI 13.7 – 16.3). Participants with an UPSIT < 10th %ile had a higher odds of SBR < 65% compared to participants with an UPSIT 10th – 15th %ile (OR 3.01, 95% CI 1.85 – 4.91).

Figure: DAT-SPECT compared to UPSIT by aSynSAA among participants recruited remotely without a PD diagnosis. Type 1 signal (high fluorescence) is predominantly found in neuronal synuclein disease; Type 2 signal (low fluorescence) in patients with glial cytoplasmic inclusions and/or clinical presentations of MSA.

RESULTS (cont'd)

Overall, 55% (198/358) of cases with UPSIT < 15th %ile and DAT-SPECT < 100% had positive aSynSAA, which increased to 71% (182/257) when selecting for more severe hyposmia (< 10th %ile). Clinical measurements did not differ substantially between people with and without detectable aSynSAA. Note that many of the participants are still in the eligibility pipeline and will be included in future analysis.

Table 1: Characteristics of participants with aSynSAA processed. ^p<0.05, *p<0.01, **p<0.001.

Mean (SD) or n(%)	aSyn SAA+, (N=198)	aSyn SAA-, (N=160)
Age	68.1 (5.0)**	65.4 (4.7)
Female	99 (50%) **	128 (80%)
UPSIT Percentile	5.3 (3.1) **	9.5 (4.2)
UPSIT < 10 th Percentile	182 (92%) **	75 (47%)
DAT-SPECT % Expected	67.7 (19.7) **	80.9 (12.1)
DAT-SPECT Categories		
< 65%	77 (39%)	14 (9%)
65% - < 80%	60 (30%)	59 (37%)
80% - < 100%	58 (29%)	87 (54%)
100% +	3 (2%)	0
MDS-UPDRS		
Part I	6.9 (5.1)	6.2 (4.9)
Part II	2.4 (4.0)	1.7 (3.2)
Part III	5.1 (6.1)*	3.6 (4.2)
Total	14.2 (11.8)^	11.4 (9.2)
RBDSQ	5.2 (4.2)**	3.0 (2.7)
SCOPA-AUT	10.6 (6.4)	9.9 (7.1)
MoCA	26.8 (2.2)	27.1 (2.2)

CONCLUSION

Remote identification of hyposmic participants can efficiently identify a cohort with a high proportion of biomarkers related to alpha-synucleinopathy. Refinement with screening questionnaires and stricter thresholds for hyposmia may improve efficiency further.

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